

Populist (dis)engagement with international parliamentary institutions: Central Europeans in the EP and PACE

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Appendix A1. EP and PACE resolutions included in the vote analysis

institution	topic	text_id	vote_date	text_title
EP	rule of law	P9_TA(2020)0014	2020-01-16	Ongoing hearings under Article 7(1) TEU regarding Poland and Hungary
		P9_TA(2020)0225	2020-01-17	Determination of a clear risk of a serious breach by Poland of the rule of law
		P9_TA(2020)0251	2020-01-17	The establishment of an EU Mechanism on Democracy, the Rule of Law and Fundamental Rights
		P9_TA(2020)0360	2020-12-16	MFF, Rule of Law Conditionality and Own Resources
		P9_TA(2021)0439	2021-10-21	The Rule of law crisis in Poland and the primacy of EU law
		P9_TA(2022)0204	2022-05-05	Ongoing hearings under Article 7(1) TEU regarding Poland and Hungary
		P9_TA(2022)0324	2022-09-15	Existence of a clear risk of a serious breach by Hungary of the values on which the Union is founded
		P9_TA(2023)0011	2023-01-18	Human rights and democracy in the world and the European Union's policy on the matter - annual report 2022
	P9_TA(2023)0216	2023-06-01	Breaches of the rule of law and fundamental rights in Hungary and frozen EU funds	
	migration	P9_TA(2024)0177	2024-04-10	Common procedure for international protection in the Union
		P9_TA(2024)0186		Standards for the reception of applicants for international protection (recast)
		P9_TA(2024)0183		Establishment of 'Eurodac' for the comparison of fingerprints for the effective application of Regulation (EU) No 604/2013, for identifying an illegally staying third-country national or stateless person and on requests for the comparison with Eurodac data by Member States' law enforcement authorities and Europol for law enforcement purposes
		P9_TA(2024)0185		Standards for the qualification of third-country nationals or stateless persons as beneficiaries of international protection
		P9_TA(2024)0184		Union Resettlement Framework
		P9_TA(2024)0178		Addressing situations of crisis and force majeure
		P9_TA(2024)0181		Screening of third-country nationals at the external borders
		P9_TA(2024)0179		Asylum and migration management

		P9_TA(2024)0180		Establishing a return border procedure, and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1148	
	Russia-Ukraine War	P9_TA(2022)0052	2022-03-01	Russian aggression against Ukraine	
		P9_TA(2022)0249	2022-06-23	Candidate status of Ukraine, the Republic of Moldova and Georgia	
		P9_TA(2022)0296	2022-07-07	Exceptional macro-financial assistance to Ukraine	
		P9_TA(2022)0405	2022-11-23	Recognising the Russian Federation as a state sponsor of terrorism	
		P9_TA(2023)0056	2023-02-16	One year of Russia's invasion and war of aggression against Ukraine	
		P9_TA(2023)0125	2023-05-09	EU/Euratom/Ukraine Association Agreement: temporary trade liberalisation supplementing trade concessions applicable to Ukrainian products	
		P9_TA(2023)0247	2023-06-15	Sustainable reconstruction and integration of Ukraine into the Euro-Atlantic community	
		P9_TA(2024)0119	2024-02-29	The need for unwavering EU support for Ukraine, after two years of Russia's war of aggression against Ukraine	
PACE	rule of law	Doc. 15025	2020-01-28	The functioning of democratic institutions in Poland	
		Doc. 15486	2022-04-28	Safeguarding and promoting genuine democracy in Europe	
		Doc. 15544	2022-06-21	The continuing need to restore human rights and the rule of law in the North Caucasus region	
		Doc. 15545	2022-06-21	Reported cases of political prisoners in the Russian Federation	
		Doc. 15618	2022-10-12	The honouring of obligations and commitments by Türkiye	
		Doc. 15619	2022-10-12	The honouring of membership obligations to the Council of Europe by Hungary	
		Doc. 15826	2023-10-10	The challenge of far-right ideology to democracy and human rights in Europe	
		Doc. 15892	2024-01-25	A democratic future for Belarus	
	migration	Doc. 15966	2024-04-17	Alexei Navalny's death and the need to counter Vladimir Putin's totalitarian regime and its war on democracy	
		Doc. 15592	2022-10-12	Safe third countries for asylum seekers	
		Doc. 15785	2023-06-21	Integration of migrants and refugees: benefits for all parties involved	
	Russia-Ukraine War	Doc. 15786	2023-06-21	Social inclusion of migrants, refugees and internally displaced persons through sport	
		Doc. 15477	2022-03-15	Consequences of the Russian Federation's aggression against Ukraine	
		Doc. 15510	2022-04-28	The Russian Federation's aggression against Ukraine: ensuring accountability for serious violations of international humanitarian law and other international crimes	
		Doc. 15631	2022-10-13	Further escalation in the Russian Federation's aggression against Ukraine	
		Doc. 15689	2023-01-26	Legal and human rights aspects of the Russian Federation's aggression against Ukraine	
			Doc. 15842	2023-10-12	Ensuring a just peace in Ukraine and lasting security in Europe

		Doc. 15821	2023-10-12	The role of the Council of Europe in preventing conflicts, restoring credibility of international institutions and promoting global peace
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